

Application of Project-Based Learning and Lean tools in a machining area of a welding industry

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Abstract

This paper has the objective of applying Project-Based Learning to propose improvements and measure the movement times in the machining area, using the Value Stream Mapping and Spaghetti Diagram as tools. This was a study developed by Graduation Students in Production Engineering of the Fluminense Federal University in partnership with a welding industry. The methodology can be classified as exploratory and descriptive, applying the bibliographic method to understand concepts related to machining, lean manufacturing, Value Stream Mapping (VSM) and Spaghetti Diagram, and it is also a case study, using the machining area of a welding industry as an analysis unit. The practices of project management recommended by the PMBOK Guide from Project Management Institute (PMI) were used, as well as the Project-Based Learning (PBL) methodology to drive the study in terms of research and application in the analysis unit. The activities of the machining area were mapped through the Value Stream Mapping and Spaghetti Diagram in order to identify the non-productive movements and time. Considering the results from the bibliographic search and the process mapping, alterations were proposed in the layout and order of activities and also, removed the ones that do not add value to the product. The improvements suggested to the welding industry were implemented and resulted in a reduction of 33h, equivalent to around EUR 5.000.

Keywords: Project-Based Learning; Lean Manufacturing; Value Stream Mapping; Machining.

1 Introduction

When a project is presented to students simply “because they will need the knowledge in the future” or “because they will need to understand it for the next subjects”, there is no natural engagement and motivation required for students to feel challenged to solve the problems of a given situation (LARMER et al., 2010). In this way, an approach which offers the investigation of authentic and real problems is needed.

Project-Based Learning (PBL) is a student-centered, teacher-facilitated learning methodology where students search for knowledge by asking questions. Such questions guide the research, which is supervised by the professor (BELL, 2010). In addition, PBL can be considered as a model that organizes learning around projects, (THOMAS, 2000).

In this context, the paper was developed by Graduation Students in Production Engineering from the Fluminense Federal University (UFF) of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, with a company in the welding industry. Considering that there is downtime and non-productive hours in the machining sector, the students defined the central question as “How to reduce downtime in a machining sector through PBL using Lean Manufacturing as the main driver?” The students defined as specific questions “How does the machining process work?” and “Which is the most appropriate Lean tool for reducing downtime?”. Both questions aimed to answer the central question.

This paper has the following structure: first, the bibliographic research will be addressed. Next, the methodological description for the academic project is presented and finally, the results and conclusion.

2 Bibliographic research

This topic will present the results of the bibliographic research done to provide theoretical basis to all improvements suggested to the welding company.

2.1 Machining

According to Davim (2008), "machining is the broad term used to describe the removal of material from a workpiece". Also, it is called an operation that gives the part shape, dimensions and surface finishes by removing the material in the form of shavings.

Machining has two types of processes, conventional and unconventional. In conventional processes, cutting operations use mechanical energy to remove material from the part. In unconventional machining processes, cutting operations use other forms of energy, such as thermoelectric power (MACHADO et al, 2015).

With the technological advances in machine tools, there was the emergence of automatic machines, and soon after, of Computer Numerical Control (CNC) machines. According to Silva (2014), CNC lathes transmit information in the form of movement by activating and deactivating the machine tool's features according to the sequence that has been programmed without depending on the assistance of an operator.

The question "How does the machining process work?" is answered through this topic, at the same time it helps the students understand the process in the analysis unit that relies on both conventional and CNC machining. As the central issue is focused on reducing downtime in this area, it is important to understand how the steps flow and which activities are essential and which are not.

2.2 Lean Manufacturing

According to Touriki et al (2021), Lean Manufacturing can be seen as "an amalgamated sociotechnical method aspiring to reduce waste by minimizing the manufacturing variations". In Lean view, waste can be defined as anything that does not add value to the product (GUPTA & JAIN, 2013).

The 3 M's (Muda, Mura and Muri) are Japanese terms related to different types of waste. The first, Muda, refers to uselessness and has 8 types, according to Womack and Jones (2013): excess production, waiting, unnecessary transport or movement, process excess or incorrect process, excess inventory, unnecessary movement, defects and misuse of personnel. According to Santos et al. (2011), Mura is waste related to lack of balance and Muri is waste related to overload.

Lean Manufacturing has several tools, which are applied in companies to reduce waste. Matt et al. (2013, p. 423) developed the matrix presented in Figure 01.

Type	Lean Production methods	micro	small	medium	large
Machinery and equipment	Low Cost Automation	○	●	●	●
	OEE Overall Equipment Effectiveness	○	●	●	●
	Preventive Maintenance	○	●	●	●
	Setup Time Reduction (SMED)	○	●	●	●
	Total Productive Maintenance	○	●	●	●
Material flow and layout	Cellular Manufacturing	○	●	●	●
	First in first out (FIFO)	○	●	●	●
	One-piece-flow	○	●	●	●
	Simulation software (e.g. MatFlow)	○	●	●	●
	Optimization of the supply chain	○	●	●	●
Organization and staff	Value Stream Mapping	○	●	●	●
	Work station design	○	●	●	●
	SS	○	●	●	●
	Autonomous work groups	○	●	●	●
	Benchmarking	○	●	●	●
Production planning and control	Ideas Management	○	●	●	●
	Job rotation	○	●	●	●
	Lean Office (Administration)	○	●	●	●
	Kaizen (CIP-Meetings)	○	●	●	●
	Standardisation	○	●	●	●
Quality	Just in Sequence	○	●	●	●
	Just in Time	○	●	●	●
	Kanban	○	●	●	●
	Line Balancing and Muda reduction	○	●	●	●
	Milkrun	○	●	●	●
Quality	PPS Simulation software	○	●	●	●
	Economic (optimal) lot size	○	●	●	●
	Visual Management	○	●	●	●
	FMEA	○	●	●	●
	Poka Yoke	○	●	●	●
	Quality Circles	○	●	●	●
	Quality Function Deployment	○	●	●	●
	Six-Sigma	○	●	●	●
	Statistical Process Control (SPC)	○	●	●	●
	Supplier Development	○	●	●	●
Total Quality Management	○	●	●	●	
Zero Defect (Jidoka)	○	●	●	●	

Figure 1. Types of Lean Manufacturing tools related to the organization site. Source: Matt et al. (2013, p. 423).

Considering that the company used as a case study is characterized as medium-size and the specific question “Which is the most appropriate Lean tool for reducing downtime?”, the tools listed in Material flow and layout type were analysed. Value Stream Mapping was selected as the most appropriate Lean tool for reducing downtime because is conceptualized in a critical analysis of material and information flows along the value chain, which makes it possible to highlight waste and opportunities for elimination thereof (ROTHER & SHOOK, 2003).

Typically, the Spaghetti Diagram is used in conjunction with Value Stream Mapping, due to the fact that aim of tracing a path taken by materials or information in a specific layout (Tapping & Shuker, 2010). In this way, the diagram allows the visualization of displacements and unnecessary efforts, showing and mapping the waste of movement and transport. Therefore, both VSM and Spaghetti Diagram were used.

3 Methodology

In the following topics, the research classification, analysis unit, procedures for both collecting data and bibliographic research as well as the PBL approach will be presented.

3.1 Research classification

The research can be classified as exploratory and descriptive, providing greater familiarity with the problem to make it more explicit and describing and establishing relationships between variables, respectively (GIL, 2002). Also, this work is a case study, which is the most appropriate strategy when “how” and “why” questions are defined about a set of events and something the researcher has little or no control over (YIN, 2015).

3.2 Analysis unit

The analysis unit is a German multinational in Petrópolis - RJ characterized by its productive activity focused on a cutting and welding portfolio. The company produces welding torches, air or water cooled, for use in manual, semi, or fully automated operations. The focus of this paper was in the Machining Sector, which is responsible for manufacturing components used in assembling of welding torches.

3.3 Procedures for collecting data

The students used three main sources of evidence. First, interviews with Machining employees to understand the process flow and help to answer the question “How does the machining process work?”. Also, interviews with the Managing Director and Industrial Manager to guide the students in prioritizing solutions.

Second, company documents and databases such as layout drawings and Work Orders, both to comprehend the process flow and answer the central question. And finally, observations made by the students during technical visits to the organization. These visits aimed to time each activity of the process flow for VSM.

3.4 Procedures for bibliographic research

The students divided the research into five steps: (i) searching literature on platforms through key words; (ii) organizing the articles by chronological order of citations, alphabetical order of authors and article coverage; (iii) selecting and prioritizing by choosing the most cited authors in the theme; (iv) reading and emphasizing the most relevant parts; and finally (v) writing, showing how the authors studied correlated with the topic of the research, in this way not simply summarizing their work. (TURRIONI & MELLO, 2012).

3.5 Stages for applying the PBL approach

The practices of project management recommended by the PMBOK Guide from Project Management Institute (PMI) were used for applying the PBL approach and its stages are described in the following topics.

3.5.1 1st stage – Definition of problem-situation and elaboration of the Project Opening Term

The problem-situation was defined together with the company and the questions were defined in conjunction with the professor to guide their research. According to Larmer et al (2010), a good guiding question captures the heart of the project in clear language and is related to the content that the teacher wants the student to

learn at that moment. As a deliverable of this stage, the Project Opening Term was elaborated containing the justifications, objective, benefits, project leader and team, sponsor as well as estimated deadline.

3.5.2 2nd stage – Elaboration of the Project Management Plan

The students prepared the Project Management Plan, which is contained the number of visits in the analysis unit and deadlines to answer the questions. For Thomas (2000), a PBL project should not be carried out under controlled conditions, in laboratories, limited by professors or by a script. To be considered a PBL project, there must not be a pre-determined product nor a pre-defined path to follow, students spend more time without professor supervision, rather having autonomy to seek the necessary knowledge and skills. Therefore, the action plan should be defined only as a support for the students during the project.

3.5.3 3rd and 4th stages – Project execution and control

The execution was done with the professor’s support, being necessary for students to acquire the required knowledge and understanding to define possible solutions and evaluate possibilities according to the literature and the context of the project. These stages aimed to respond the central question through the bibliographic research, interviews, company documents and database as well as visits to the organization. Also, it aimed to elaborate the VSM and Spaghetti Diagram.

3.5.4 5th stage – Project ending

In the Ending stage, the project’s product is publicly presented not only to the professor, but also to a relevant audience – in this case, the company stakeholders. In this way, the meaning of the entire project-based learning process is reinforced (LARMER et al., 2010).

4 Results

Next, the results of the activities described in Methodology are presented. This topic was structured in two parts: analysis of the problem situation and proposals for improvement.

4.1 Analysis of the problem-situation

The scope of this study is the processes performed before and after machining a part and not the manufacturing process itself. The students divided the problem-situation into three processes and analysed its current scenario. The bibliographic research, interviews and questions guided all the improvements proposed by the students.

4.1.1 Current scenario – Value Steam Mapping of WIP shelf process

Work in-process (WIP) parts correspond to assembled items that still need to be machined. The activities in the process flow are represented by boxes in VSM as shown in Figure 2. In VSMs, all the cycle times (CT) were timed by the students during visits to the organization and the order of activities was collected through the interviews.

Figure 2. VSM of WIP shelf process – current scenario.

According to Figure 2, the last activity highlighted in red means that there is an opportunity for improvement. In current scenario, the employee takes the parts to the finished products shelf outside the Machining sector. The students proposed to place this shelf within the sector to reduce movement time.

4.1.2 Current scenario – Value Steam Mapping of raw material shelf process

The raw materials used in the Machining sector are brass or copper bars that are stored inside the Warehouse. Focusing only on the highlighted activities in Figure 3, after checking if it's a WIP or raw material Production Order (PO), the employee waits for the PO booking in the Warehouse. The students proposed this booking process to be after finishing the PO. And the last activity was covered in the previous topic.

Figure 3. VSM of raw material shelf – current scenario.

Removing the waiting for the PO booking, the students followed the Lean Manufacturing most important principle of reducing waste and consequently, downtime. It is important to emphasize how valuable is the PBL projects, due to the fact that the students are able to apply the knowledge learned during bibliographic research.

4.1.3 Current scenario – Value Steam Mapping of exchange of shavings barrels process

Shavings are produced during the machining and in this case, shavings coming from the Computer Numerical Control (CNC) Turning Center will be analysed. The students proposed removing the first two activities highlighted in red, because the pallet trucks and the barrel area should be within the Machining sector, avoiding movement time between areas.

Figure 4. VSM of exchange of shavings barrels – current scenario.

According to Figure 4, the activities of placing the full barrel and pallet truck in the appropriate area should be done after restarting the machining process. Then, the parts would continue being manufactured while the employee does these activities.

4.1.4 Current scenario – Spaghetti Diagram

The Spaghetti Diagram was built to analyse the movement and trajectory of employees in the Machining sector when they need to pick up a tool or instrument that helps them in machining parts. In it, the coloured lines represent the trajectory of the employees starting from each machine and going to each cabinet. These movements can be seen in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Spaghetti Diagram – current scenario.

It was identified that the employees needed to move around a lot to find the instruments and tools that were scattered around the cabinets in the Machining sector. Therefore, it was proposed creating a tooling and instrumentation room. With this, the employees’ trajectories would start from their machines to a specific place, not needing to go around the entire sector looking for instruments and tools.

4.2 Improvements proposal

After analysing the current scenarios of all processes selected for this study, improvements were proposed to the welding company as previously showed. This topic is divided into two parts: compare the results from both current and future VSMs and present the Spaghetti Diagram after the tooling and instrumentation room.

4.2.1 Future scenario – VSM of all processes

From the comparison of data from the Current and Future Value Stream Maps, it was possible to quantify the gains obtained by the proposed improvements suggested for the sector. The process efficiency calculation is obtained by dividing the time that adds value to the process by the lead time. Therefore, the following values shown in Table 1 were obtained.

Table 1. Comparison of VSM results – current and future scenarios.

Process	Criteria	Current	Future	Percentage
WIP shelf	Cycle time	637,93	637,93	0,00%
	Value added time	600,00	600,00	0,00%
	No added value time	98,51	84,42	14,30%
	Lead time	698,51	684,42	2,02%
	Process cycle efficiency (%)	86%	88%	2%
Raw material shelf	Cycle time	698,47	637,69	8,70%
	Value added time	600,00	600,00	0,00%
	No added value time	194,40	88,83	54,31%
	Lead time	794,40	688,83	13,29%
	Process cycle efficiency (%)	76%	87%	12%
	Cycle time	147,69	121,02	18,0%

Exchange of shavings barrels	Value added time	60,00	60,00	0,00%
	No added value time	250,41	93,70	62,58%
	Lead time	310,41	153,70	50,48%
	Process cycle efficiency (%)	19%	39%	20%

All the results presented on Table 1 are regarding one execution of each process. Together with the Machining Supervisor during the interview and according to the company's database, it was identified how many times each process is done weekly and with this, the annual gain in hours was calculated, which can be used by the employee in other activities that add value to the organization.

Table 2. Annual gain in hours.

Criteria / Process	WIP shelf	Raw material shelf	Exchange of shavings barrels	Total
Estimate of process execution / week	20	15	4	39
Estimate of process execution / year	960	720	192	1.872
Annual gain (h)	3,76 h	21,12 h	8,36 h	33,24 h
Value of man-hour (EUR)	EUR 151,00	EUR 151,00	EUR 151,00	EUR 151,00
Reduction in costs (EUR)	EUR 567,76	EUR 3.189,12	EUR 1.262,36	EUR 5.019,24

As it can be seen on Table 2, all the improvements would result in a reduction of 33,24h annually, which is equivalent to a cost saving of EUR 5.019,24. These hours can be invested in activities that add value to the product, considering that all proposals were implemented.

4.2.2 Spaghetti Diagram after improvements

After implementing the tooling and instrumentation room and aiming better visualize the movement flow in the new layout model, a future Spaghetti Diagram was prepared.

Figure 6. Spaghetti Diagram – future scenario.

Comparing both Figures 5 and 6, the main reason to significantly reduce the movements inside the Machining sector is the creation of a tooling and instrumentation room. The green highlights are the layout improvements.

5 Conclusion

This paper aimed to conduct a project through PBL by applying the Value Stream Mapping and the Spaghetti Diagram in the machining process, having as central question "How to reduce downtime in a Machining sector through PBL using Lean Manufacturing as the main driver?" The students were oriented by the professor to define specific questions to help answering the central one: "How does the machining process work?" and "Which is the most appropriate Lean tool for reducing downtime?".

The PBL methodology divided the project into five stages, where the first one defined the problem-situation with the analysis unit and helped the students to prepare the questions that would guide their learning process. In the second stage, the students planned the activities within the organization and bibliographic research in terms of deadlines.

In the third and fourth stages, they had to answer the questions. For “How does the machining process work?”, the students learned through the bibliographic research, interviews with the Machining employees and visiting the company. And for “Which is the most appropriate Lean tool for reducing downtime?”, by searching in literature and interviewing the Managing Director and Industrial Manager, the Value Stream Mapping and Spaghetti Diagram were selected as the most appropriate Lean tools for reducing downtime.

As a result of elaborating the VSM of each process, it became possible to identify and eliminate some activities that did not add value to it, reducing the lead time of the processes. Regarding the Spaghetti Diagram, it helped to define an ideal layout for the machining sector, eliminating unnecessary employee paths. With the suggested improvement proposals, there was an annual reduction of 33 hours in activities, which can be used in a better way by the employee, performing activities that add value to the process and that optimize the productivity of the organization. These 33 hours are equivalent to EUR 5.019,24.

Finally, the fifth stage of presenting the project, it is clear that the central question “How to reduce downtime in a machining sector through PBL using Lean Manufacturing as the main driver?” was answered. Not only by following the PBL staged, applying the methodology and answering the specific questions, but effectively reducing downtime in an average of 50%. This result shows how important is for students in participating in academic PBL projects and in partnership with industries, because it gives students the experience of how to solve real problems within an organization. Another important benefit of this type of project is being able to guide students in determining the area of Production Engineering that they most identify with.

In addition, through the study, it was possible to apply the knowledge obtained in the academic environment and participate in the implementation process of the proposed solution. In this sense, students had the opportunity to live experiences in an industry, while still in the academic period, thus providing learning outside the university, a balance between theory and practice.

This paper was also very beneficial for the students in three main aspects: first, the approach to the academic environment, in writing an article and looking for the best references on the subject; the deepening of the vision through the process, increasing criticality and the search for better solutions that fit the specificity of the process and, finally, the possibility of understanding how the company and the job market work.

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